

SITE GPR	YEAR 10	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.7588 Max: 62.9483	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1205 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	 University of Michigan Kelsey Museum of Archaeology Gabii Project	
	In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No			Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 717-719
DEFINITION Brownish soil with stones below 1181				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1181	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction		FORMATION PROCESS 1204 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition					
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are				SOIL/MATRIX			
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		clay 15% silt 85% sand ___%	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery m <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae r <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dolia r <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) m <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Travertine r <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones r <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
				Compaction		Color	
				<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft		<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original	
Northern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Southern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Western Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit					
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE							
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:				Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1181, 1204				Covers: 1223, 1224, 1001			
Is cut by:				Cuts:			
Is filled by:				Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS Greco-Italian Amphora within layer - Pictures #749-750, complete rim and tops of handles present; found upside down. Excavated with pickaxe, (see sketch for location)							
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: Near center at Southern edge of excavation Shape: Rectangular, with stones 1206 jutting in at SE.							
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): level. Rubble visible at surface throughout Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) amount of rubble fairly uniform throughout. Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): slightly thinner around center of room. Nature of the interface with layer below: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)							
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North): SU 1153 "Room 1" 1001 1205				

 = walls
 = slightly larger stones
 = pottery in situ (see observations)
 x = Rubby surface

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Layer of soil and rubble placed upon bedrock in order to level the surface for construction of building. Western and southern walls of room 1 appear to be built directly on this rubble. Layer appears to continue beneath northern wall of Room 1. There is a shallow, curving channel in the bedrock beneath the layer; this layer appears to have filled the channel as well.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by S. Pous J. Farr

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Entered by

on